

Two-dimensional self-heating from HEMTs down to cryogenic temperatures

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Abstract— The recent developments in quantum computing architectures have caused an increasing interest in cryogenic low-noise amplifiers (LNAs), due to their role in the qubit readout chain. Advanced quantum computers with many qubits will require cryogenic integration of thousands of LNAs. Minimizing LNA power dissipation while maintaining low noise will be of key importance due to the limited available cooling power in cryostats. In addition, self-heating and heat dissipation of cryogenic low-noise amplifiers represent limiting factors in the device's performance and integration. While self-heating is predicted to increase in transistor channels at cryogenic temperatures, large-scale self-heating outside of active devices is not well understood. In this paper, the two-dimensional heat flow due to the self-heating of InGaAs/InP high electron mobility transistors (HEMTs) is experimentally studied. We realize a matrix of Schottky diode thermal sensors close to the active device, which allows us to obtain a full two-dimensional temperature mapping with respect to the power dissipated by the HEMT. Measurements are performed in the temperature range of 300 K to 4.2 K. Results indicate that HEMT large-scale self-heating is suppressed at lower ambient temperatures. Below 77 K, the increase of surface temperature at a distance $< 12 \mu\text{m}$ from the active area is less than the measurement sensitivity (0.5 K). Based on these results we conclude that the increased self-heating in the channel at cryogenic conditions does not result in increased surface heating. These results build on our understanding of the opportunities for integrated cryogenic electronics in quantum computers.

Index Terms— self-heating, cryogenics electronics, HEMT, quantum applications

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum computers promise to solve problems that are currently intractable with classical computing architectures [1]. To do so, they use quantum processors, which are operated in dilution refrigerators at deep-cryogenic temperatures. The signals needed to control these devices are currently generated outside the cryostat [2]. Interfacing classical control electronics with quantum processors represents a challenge to the scalability of the quantum system. For this reason, there are significant research activities in the integration of CMOS electronics inside the cryostat [3]. Power dissipation is one of the main design constraints for such classical electronics, especially for integration as close as possible to the quantum processor. The 4 K temperature stage is a viable option for

active electronics given the relatively high available cooling power [4]. Such electronics are already today integrated in the cryostat, in the form of low-noise amplifiers (LNAs) at the 4 K stage [5]. Extremely low noise, i.e., a minimum noise temperature of < 5 K with 40 dB gain at 4-8 GHz frequencies, together with low power dissipation, < 5 mW, is required. InGaAs/InP high electron mobility transistors (InP HEMTs) can meet these specifications due to the relatively narrow band gap and high electron mobility [6][7].

In recent studies, extremely low-power LNAs operating in cryogenic conditions have been demonstrated [5]. Self-heating (SH) in these devices is shown to affect device characteristics, which becomes even more evident at cryogenic temperatures. Choi [8] and Schlee [9] demonstrated experimentally that SH increases drastically at cryogenic temperatures for InP HEMTs. In addition, the heat generated can spread to adjacent devices, inducing thermal positive loops [10]. This can be detrimental not only to cryogenic circuits but also to the integration of electronics and qubits, which are particularly sensitive to thermal crosstalk and noise [11]. SH characterization efforts have so far focussed on the gate temperature of standard and SOI MOSFET technologies to improve performances at room temperature [12]–[15]. Only recently has attention moved to cryogenic temperatures due to quantum computing applications [16]–[19]. Conventional measurement techniques rely on non-contact methods, such as IR microscopy [20] or micro-Raman spectroscopy [21][22], that are limited by geometrical constraints, such as the buried nature of the gate channel and the gate lengths of these devices. Another technique used is gate thermometry, that can provide useful information on the SH even at cryogenic temperatures [17] [18], with the limitation of allowing to measure the temperature only at the gate of the transistor. In such conditions, higher channel temperature has been reported for both silicon CMOS and III-V HEMTs. Choi [8] used the gate-to-channel junction temperature dependence to assess the thermal resistance of HEMT structures, showing trends comparable to those for Si CMOS. In addition, large-scale SH, i.e. the heat flow from the active region to the surrounding, has been studied for Si CMOS by thermal sensing devices close to the heat source [10][17]. In Si CMOS, integration of sensor diodes and active transistors can be done through standard foundry technologies. Similar studies have not yet been performed for InGaAs/InP HEMT platforms. As a

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Figure 1 Simplified schematics and layout of the HEMT and sensing diode structure. The biasing of the diodes is displayed on the right. V_g , V_d and V_b are the bias voltages, respectively for the gate, the drain and the diodes. The active sensing area marks the region where the temperature is measured. Identical structures but with the active sensing area displaced in the X-direction were also fabricated.

result, large-scale SH effects in such devices remain a topic of interest.

In this work, a matrix of III-V Schottky diode thermal sensors is integrated with active HEMTs, to map the two-dimensional self-heating. Although channel self-heating has been shown to increase significantly at cryogenic temperatures for Si FETs and InGaAs/InP HEMTs, we demonstrate in this work that, contrary to expectations, cryogenic operation results in reduced large-scale self-heating. Our study expands the understanding of the opportunities and limitations of HEMT devices in quantum computer applications.

II. DEVICES AND METHODS

A custom test structure, shown in Fig. 1, was designed and fabricated. The device under test (DUT) is an InP/InGaAs HEMT with structure and performance similar to commercial cryo-HEMT technologies. The gate width is kept constant at 10 μm , while three different gate lengths L_g were investigated: 150, 250 and 400 nm. Located at different distances in x- and y-directions is a matrix of Schottky diode thermal sensors.

Every test cell is composed of six Schottky devices, with distance in the y-direction of each device from the gate of the HEMT of 0.75, 2.75, 4.75, 7.15, 9.5 and 12.2 μm . Multiple devices were realized, where the sensing structure composed by the Schottky devices is shifted along the x-direction with respect to the HEMT. This allows to characterize areas of the surface that are not aligned with the gate. We designed nine different x-positions, to be able to gather temperature data across a 2D area of the surface around the DUT. The distance along the x-axis of each design from the gate of the HEMT was varied from -2.12 to 2.12 μm . Fig. 1 shows the structure with zero x-axis displacement, where the centre of the active sensing area is aligned with the right edge of the HEMT's gate.

Figure 2 Sensing Schottky diode SEM micrograph. The green highlighted area represents the biasing contact and the blue one the ground connection. The active area is highlighted in red, it presents a smaller width with respect to rest of the heterostructure due to the underetch of the channel layer during fabrication.

Both the HEMT and the sensors were realized on the same III-V heterostructure which enables a tight integrated structure. The heterostructure was grown by molecular beam epitaxy on an InP wafer, and is formed by the following epitaxial layers (starting from the closest to the substrate): an InAlAs buffer layer, an InGaAs quantum well that forms the channel of both HEMTs and diodes, a spacer and a barrier layer both made of InAlAs and separated by a delta-doping region of Si impurities that tune the potential inside the transistor channel, and finally a highly-doped InGaAs cap layer.

The mobility in the quantum well reaches about $45,000 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ when cooled to 4.2 K, making it suitable HF operation. The cap layer allows the formation of low-resistance ohmic contacts, realized by deposition of a Ni/Ge/Au multilayer metal structure. The gate metal consisting of a Ti/Pt/Au stack was deposited after etching the capping layer. The devices were passivated through Al_2O_3 deposition.

Despite the effort in reducing the gate leakage current, the gate-to-channel junction of HEMTs behaves as a Schottky diode [8][23]. Therefore, one contact (in our case the drain) is left unconnected to obtain a two-terminal Schottky diode which acts as a sensor for the temperature measurement.

In Fig. 2 an SEM micrograph of one of the sensing diodes is presented. The mean width and length of the Schottky diode active region are 565 nm and 194 nm, respectively. The red area indicates the effective active region of the Schottky diode. The bias voltage is applied on the pad to the right while the left pad is grounded. The bias is connected to the active area through a metal connection, realized in the same way as the HEMT transistor gate. The diode characteristic is presented in Fig. 3a and shows exponential behaviour for forward biasing among a wide range of temperatures. At low voltages, the temperature sensitivity is enhanced above 350 K, whereas above 0.3 V the sensitivity is relatively small for the entire temperature range.

Figure 3 (a) Logarithmic plot of diode current for different ambient temperature, from 300K to 410K. (b) Diode voltage as a function of the ambient temperature for different bias current. (c) Diode voltage from 4K to 300K of Schottky diode for a bias current of 2 μ A.

We used the temperature dependence of the diode voltage when biased with a fixed current to assess the mean temperature across the active area of the device. In a simple model, without considering carrier recombination inside the depletion region, the voltage of a Schottky diode is given by:

$$V_b = \ln\left(\frac{I}{AR}\right) \frac{k_b T}{q} - 2 \frac{k_b T}{q} \ln(T) + \frac{\phi_b}{q}$$

where A is the area of the active region, R is the Richardson's constant, ϕ_b is the barrier potential and V_b is the applied bias to the metal. At first approximation, the voltage can be assumed linear with respect to the temperature. Experimental data confirms that the device characteristics satisfy the expectations, as reported in Fig. 3b, due to the linear trend at high current densities. The voltage response to the temperature slightly deviates from the linearity for biasing currents smaller than 1 μ A. Therefore, the devices have been calibrated at 2 μ A bias current. The linear coefficient is extracted experimentally for every single device to ensure the correct level of accuracy of the results. The diode voltage has been measured for different surface temperatures for every device and the sensitivity has been calculated, fitting the curve with a first-degree polynomial.

III. ANALYSIS

Fig. 3c displays the calibration measurement for a representative device in the temperature range from 4 K to 300 K. For high temperatures, the linear model stays accurate, but below 150 K the approximation becomes too simplistic and the voltage starts following an empirical quadratic trend. However, the ΔT induced by the SH at lower temperatures is small enough to locally approximate the quadratic trend with a linear dependency. Below 50 K the devices sensitivity begins to decrease, even though it peaks before reaching 4.2 K. This has been found also in other electrical characteristics, such as V_{th} , in the same HEMT technology [24]. Having the same active region composition, the change in the Schottky barrier height and V_{th} share the same underlying principle.

We record the change in the diode voltage V_g as a function of the power dissipated by the HEMT, $P = I_{DS} \times V_{DS}$. Finally, we repeated this process for different ambient temperatures.

In Fig. 4a room temperature measurements of one full array of devices are presented. The ΔT is related to the power flows through the relation $\Delta T = P \times R_{th}$, where P is the power dissipated and R_{th} is the thermal resistance.

The measured temperature as a function of the dissipated power is linear as presented in Fig. 4a. Therefore, the thermal resistance can be assumed constant given the small ΔT in these experiments. We used this conclusion to process the raw data and remove additional noise caused by the measurement setup. The following steps are followed to eliminate these noise effects and extract only the effective thermal signal:

- Extraction of main linear trend
- Low pass filter to select the low-frequency noise
- Subtraction of the selected noise from the signal
- Linear fit of the filtered signal
- Elimination of residual vertical shift
- Mean of multiple curves taken in the same bias condition

This allows setting correctly the reference value for no power dissipation and thus comparing different sensing devices. Fig. 4a shows the post-processed results which agree with similar devices realized for CMOS characterization [17].

IV. ONE DIMENSIONAL HEAT PROFILES

The method described in Sec. III is now employed to measure the surface temperature in the full operating range of the HEMT, up to saturation. The drain voltage is swept from 0 to 0.8 V and the gate voltage is kept constant. The right pad of the HEMT (See Fig. 1) has been consistently used as a drain. The diode voltage is recorded while the drain voltage is changed. The same experiment has been performed while keeping stable the current through the HEMT and has provided temperature

Figure 4 (a) Surface ΔT as a function of dissipated power by a HEMT at 300K. Each color corresponds to a different distance of the sensing device with respect to the HEMT. All devices in this figure belong to the centred array aligned with the HEMT gate. (b) One dimensional substrate ΔT of a 250 nm gate length HEMT measured for 5 mW of power dissipation, together with the gate thermometry at 300K (red square). The complete dataset has been fitted with an hyperbolic function. (c) One dimensional surface ΔT for three different HEMT gate lengths for a power dissipation of 5 mW at 300K. Each point corresponds to one sensing diode of the centred array aligned with the HEMT gate. (d) X-direction surface ΔT distribution for different distances along the y-direction at 300K and 5 mW power dissipation.

values that strongly match the measurement performed in Fig. 4a, ensuring that the thermal time constant of the system is below the time constant of the current change through the HEMT. Therefore, it is possible to assume that the sensing device temperature is always in equilibrium with the HEMT device dissipation. The continuous recording of the voltage has been preferred due to lower acquisition time and increased accuracy. A sweep of the HEMT drain voltage is performed for each single sensing device separately and the measured voltage is converted to a temperature value using the calibration measurements shown in Fig. 3c. Room temperature measurements have been employed to verify the methodology and its performance.

The temperature distribution along the y-axis, as described in Fig. 1, is first presented in Fig. 4b. At 5 mW power dissipation the temperature reaches an increase of more than 2 K at 0.8 μm from the power device and saturates at around 0.5 K at larger distances. This behaviour is qualitatively similar to [17] and

[25], following a $1/d^n$ law (where d is the distance and n is a factor between 1.09 and 1.10 at 5 mW). Gate thermometry has also been performed on similar devices. At room temperature, the measured gate temperature reaches 13 K. This additional data point has been used to fit the data available with a hyperbolic function, as presented in Fig. 4b. Deriving the intrinsic self-heating from the external as measured by the sensing diodes is not straightforward, since it depends on the thermal parameters of a complex heterostructure and associated design, including metallization. Note that the different gate lengths do not have a distinct impact on the surface heating, as presented in Fig. 4c. Both the temperature and the overall trend agree for the different devices.

V. TWO-DIMENSIONAL HEATMAP

The measurements performed for a single array have been repeated for the different x-axis positions of the sensing diode structure, as reported in Sec. II. Nine different sensing diode

Figure 5 Heatmap generated for a 5 mW power dissipation at 300K attached on top of a SEM micrograph of one of the sensing structures. A sensing diode array with metal connections to bias each device is shown in blue and the HEMT in red. Each point of the heatmap corresponds to one measurement of a sensing diode.

arrays have been measured to generate a full temperature map. From the collected data, we have built a graphical representation in two dimensions to show the surface heating around the device. Fig. 5 shows the heatmap for 5 mW power dissipation overlaid on an SEM image of one of the structures. Each point of the heatmap corresponds to one sensing diode that has been characterized. The HEMT responsible for the power dissipation is highlighted in red, whereas the blue region represents the metallization of one sensing diode array. The uncertainty in the data is mainly due to device-to-device variations for the sensing diodes.

The HEMT power dissipation is used as a normalizing parameter so that intra-device variability effects on the results are strongly reduced. At 300 K, the temperature near the metal connections to the source and drain remains close to the peak value, even at larger lateral distances of 2 μm . This means that these structures play a fundamental role in heat dissipation. However, the temperature peak is positioned in the centre of the structure and the temperature decreases when moving laterally as reported in Fig. 4d. This difference is less evident for larger y-distances. This means that the actual heat source is localized, but at larger distances, the metal pads are responsible for the temperature distribution. It was reported that the self-heating is expected to be concentrated on the drain side due to ballistic transport [26]. This effect can be observed here since the central sensing vertical array is centred on the edge of the HEMT's gate and presents the highest temperature difference, although at the limit of the spatial resolution of what this method can achieve.

VI. CRYOGENIC CHARACTERIZATION

Single sensing arrays have been characterized for a range of ambient temperatures, from 300 to 4.2 K, to compare the effect of self-heating in different operating conditions. The devices are cooled through a cryogenic probe station and the same

Figure 6 Surface ΔT as a function of the distance from the gate along the y direction at various ambient temperatures ($4\text{K} < T_{\text{amb}} < 300\text{K}$). These measurements are related to a 250nm HEMT at 5 mW power dissipation. The inset reports the sensing diode voltage for different ambient temperature. Measurements are reported for the device aligned with the HEMT gate and at 0.8 μm vertical distance.

characterization described in Sec. III has been performed. Fig. 6 shows the results for the different temperatures of a 250 nm device aligned with the HEMT gate. A residual thermal signal is still present at 150 K, but the HEMT self-heating is strongly reduced for lower temperatures. All devices demonstrated heating below 0.5 K when the surface temperature is brought below 77K.

It is worth noting that the diodes' sensitivity is reduced at lower temperatures going from 1 mV/K at 300K to 0.5 mV/K at 150 K, limiting the smallest temperature differences that can be detected. Nevertheless, Fig. 6 also shows the diode voltages measurements for 4K, 10K and 20K of the closest device to the HEMT and illustrates how this voltage is not changing for the same ambient temperature, while power is increasing. At the same time changing the substrate temperature affects the diode voltage. A change of more than 3 mV is observed from 4 K to 10 K and from 10 K to 20 K. This means that the device would be able to detect changes in the temperature of the surface, despite the lower sensitivity. This lack of a thermal signal can only be explained by a reduced self-heating in the HEMTs surrounding area, considering that the variability across an entire diodes' array is lower than 0.1K at 4K. Although the temperature increase in HEMTs due to SH is expected to be greater at low temperatures, as reported in [8], [9] and in gate thermometry performed at 4K on these structures, the large-scale two-dimensional self-heating emanating from the HEMT is thus here shown to be minimal. This indicates that, under certain conditions, relatively tight integration of qubits and readout HEMTs may be possible.

In these structures, heat dissipation happens only in the InAlAs buffer layer and InP substrate since the HEMT and the sensing devices are realized through mesa etching that removes all the layers until the buffer around the active regions. On the other hand, no other thermal dissipation mechanisms are

possible. Conduction is limited by the vacuum of the measurement chamber and irradiation is negligible in these conditions.

Although only a few room temperature thermal conductivity values are found in the literature for InAlAs [27]–[29] and InGaAs [27][29][30], most common semiconductor materials, such as Si, SiO₂ and InP show a maximum in the thermal conductance in the cryogenic region followed by an exponential decrease [32]–[34]. Therefore we can assume a similar trend also for InAlAs and InGaAs with a possible shift of the temperature corresponding to the maximum thermal conductivity. Contrary to silicon FETs, we have here demonstrated that the effect of SH is limited to the active device and does not significantly spread to the surrounding area for $P < 5$ mW. The effect of interfaces and geometrical structure in addition to changes in heat diffusion regime are likely to be responsible for these discrepancies, as shown in [22] and [23].

VII. CONCLUSION

The two-dimensional self-heating of InGaAs/InP HEMTs has been characterized through sensing diode arrays from 300 K to 4.2 K. The integration of diodes in proximity to the active HEMTs enabled the experimental study of the impact of SH in the area about 100 μm^2 surrounding the active device. At room temperature, a two-dimensional heatmap reveals a peak temperature increase of 2K for $P = 5$ mW at 0.8 μm from the active device. On the other hand, at 4.2 K the increase of the surface temperature due to the HEMT self-heating is even lower than the sensitivity of the measurement (0.5 K). Although strongly increased self-heating in the channel temperature at cryogenic temperatures has previously been reported for both for CMOS and III-V HEMTs, this work showed that surface heating, in fact, reduces with the substrate temperature for InGaAs/InP HEMTs. This is likely due to the complex interplay between highly non-linear temperature-dependent thermal conductivities of semiconductors and interfaces. These results provide valuable insights relating to the future integration of cryogenic HEMT-based electronics in quantum computers.

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